

EPOXY FILM ADHESIVE FOR ALUMINUM AND COMPOSITE REPAIRING

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SUMMARY: A new carboxyl terminated butadiene-acrylonitrile (CTBN) modified epoxy film adhesive, designed as SY-41, which was mainly a mixture of diglycidyl-ether of bisphenol A and Curing agent 328, has been developed for Aluminum and Composite structure repairing . After 4 hours curing at 90°C, under pressure of 0.1MPa, the bonding strengths to Phosphoric Acid Anodizing(PAA) surface treated aluminum adherend were equivalent to those of structural adhesives curing at 120°C. The lap-shear strengths at room temperature and 82°C were 42.7MPa and 30.8Mpa, respectively., while the Bell peel strengths at room temperature and 82°C are 6.0kN/m and 8.7kN/m. After hygrothermal aging 500 hours at 70°C, R.H. 95-100%, the adhesive maintained a high retention lap-shear strength of 31MPa. In addition , the shelf life of the adhesive at room temperature is longer than 1 month.

KEYWORDS : film adhesive, toughness, field repairing , formula optimization

INTRODUCTION

The damage of aluminum (Al) alloys and composites in aircraft structures were often required to be repaired by adhesively-bonding .The adherends were usually Al-Al, Al-composite or composite-composite. The adhesives employed for these repairs need high temperature and high pressure were usually 121°C or 177°C curing epoxy film adhesives. But for field repair where electrical-heating blanket and vacuum bagging pressure were only available, such strict preparing condition was not easy to satisfy. Furthermore, the maldistribution of temperature will raise thermal residual stress because of large differences of thermal expansion coefficient between the aluminum and composite. It was reported that curing above 100°C of bonded repairs may result in blistered or deteriorated adhesive, caused by the action of absorbed moisture between laminates during the curing temperature cycle, which may result in a lower bonding strength [1].

Therefore, to develop a film adhesive curable at temperature below 100°C and vacuum pressure and with mechanical properties equivalent to those of 121°C curing film adhesives will greatly enhance the reliability of field repairing. In this paper, a CTBN modified epoxy film adhesive SY-41, curable at 90°C, with the pressure of 0.1MPa and suitable to field repair of aluminum alloys and composite structures was introduced. The formula design and optimization of the adhesive, its thermal reactive characteristics and mechanical properties of aluminum adherend bonding were also presented. Bonding properties concerning composite adherend will be discussed in another paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Process

The epoxy resins employed were two kinds of diglycidyl-ether of bisphenol A(DGEBA) having epoxide equivalent weight of approximately 220g/mole and 900 g/mole respectively and a liquid trifunctional amino-epoxy resin having epoxide equivalent weight of 120 g/mole. The curing agent was a modified amine and commercially available as Curing agent 328 . The rubber used to tough the epoxy resins was a liquid carboxyl-terminated butadiene-acrylonitrile (CTBN) with 26wt% bonding AN and above 3000 number average molecular weight(Mn).

The prepolymer was prepared by initially adding the required quantity of CTBN and epoxy resins to a stirred glass vessel followed by heating to 170°C and holding 2 hours while the Nitrogen atmosphere was used to protect the mixture from oxidation. After finishing the prepolymerization, the formed epoxy-CTBN-epoxy adducts in the mixture were confirmed by Infrared Spectra. The film adhesive was then prepared by mixing the prepolymer and Curing agent 328 in a two-roll mixer and hot pressing into film. The thickness of the film was controlled around 0.3mm.

Specimen Preparing and Testing

Adherend aluminum alloys were LY12CZ with thickness of 2mm and 0.5mm for lap-shear strength and Bell peel strength testing . All of the adherends were phosphoric acid anodized (PAA) per ASTM D3933. All of the adhesively bonded specimen were press cured at 90°C , 0.1 MPa for different time of 3 to 5 hours per design. The lap-shear strength was tested per ASTM D 1002 and the Bell peel strength was tested according to ASTM D 1876.

DSC Analysis

A Perkin Elmer Differential Scanning Calorimeter(DSC) model DSC-2, was operated to obtain DSC curves at different heating rates 5°C/min,10°C/min and 20°C/min from 25°C to 250°C under dry nitrogen.

Gel Time

Gel times were tested by probing the adhesive resin in a thermal plate at controlled temperature with a glass rod to observe long strands drawn out from the adhesive resin. Gelation is the point where no such stringing of the resin was noticed and the probed material has rubber feel. Gel time is the elapsed time when the adhesive reached the point of gelation as measured by a stop watch under the controlled temperature .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Composition of Adhesive

The toughening effect of a CTBN modified epoxy system not only depended on acrylonitrile bonding content, carboxyl content and molecular weight of CTBN and prepolymerization or not, the procedure of prepolymerization and curing agent of the resin system, but also in close relation to the type and the molecular weight of the epoxy resins. Our previous research indicated that the higher the average epoxide equivalent of the epoxy mixture, the longer the average crosslink length of epoxy matrix, which resulted in CTBN to initiate much plastic deformation energy consumption of the matrix.^[2] Both solid epoxy resin with long molecular chain and liquid epoxy resin with short molecular chain were used in the adhesive to balance its toughness and tackiness. In the mean time, a trifunctional amino-epoxy resin was used to improve crosslink density and heat resistant characteristics of the cured product.

Curing agent was a very important composition for an adhesive. A typical curing system which can cure epoxy resin around 90°C comprises three parts: (1) a room temperature stable, elevated temperature decomposable nitrogen containing compound, (2) a hydroxyl containing organic compound and (3) an organo lead or mercury compound[3]. An epoxy adhesive containing this curing system has a long ambient temperature shelf life, after 6 hours cure at 82°C, the lap shear strength of aluminum adherend is about 31MPa. Other curing system such as curing agent D and dicyandiamide plus Accelerator No.1 can also cure epoxy resins at 90-110°C.^[4,5] But none of them meets our requirement. Curing agent 328 used in this study is a modified amine, it has excellent latency at ambient temperature while reacts quickly with epoxy resins at elevated temperature.

The Optimization of the Adhesive Formula

Our previous research shows, when the quantity of epoxy resins were 100 phr(wt), 10-27.5phr CTBN and 13-23phr Curing agent 328 should be used in the adhesive formula in order to get a cured system with high crosslink density and high strength and good toughness.

The first order and second order orthogonal-regression optional design were then applied to optimize formulation of the adhesive in above mentioned scope. The curing time in the optimization experiment was settled down to 3 hours. The result showed that the confidence level of the first order regression equation was greater than 99%, but that of the second order regression equation was less than 90%. The experiment verification met to the prediction of the first order regression equation.^[6] So it can be concluded that the first order orthogonal regression experiment was successful and the regression equation can reflect the change of the adhesive characteristics in the experimental zone. According to the first order regression equation, with the help of computer, an optimum formula of the adhesive having lap shear strength of 38.8MPa and Bell peel strength of 4.83kN/m was developed. The predicted curves of the shear strength and Bell peel strength of the adhesive are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

Figure 1: The predicted shear strength curve according to the first order regression equation

Figure 2: The predicted Bell peel strength curve of the first order regression equation

The Thermal Reactive Characteristics

The gel time-temperature curve of SY-41 was shown in Fig. 3. It was obvious that the slope of the curve changes greatly in the temperature range of 80-100°C, which indicated that the polymerization of the adhesive reacts greatly and the curing temperature of the adhesive can be selected in the range of 80-100°C. The apparent activation energy before gel calculated according to Flory's gel theory was 68.5kJ/mole. [7]

Figure 3: The gel time-temperature curve of SY-41

DSC analysis results of different heating rate of 5°C/min, 10°C/min, 20°C/min and extrapolation to 0 °C/min were listed in Table 1. T_{onset} and T_{peak} in the table mean the curing onset temperature and peak exotherm temperature of the DSC curves respectively. The apparent activation energy of the whole curing reaction calculated based on Kissinger's method was 93.2 kJ/mole.^[8] According to Table 1, the best curing temperature range should be 105°C-119°C. But if prolong the curing time, excellent adhesion properties can still be obtained when cure the adhesive at 90°C which will be confirmed in the following experiment.

Table 1: The characteristic Temperature of DSC curves at different heating rate

heating rate, °C/min	T_{onset} , °C	T_{peak} , °C
5	110	125
10	117	132
20	127	143
0	105	119

The Study of the Curing Procedure

The optimum formula adhesive has a high shear strength and a low peel strength, this may be attribute to the short curing time and low crosslink density because of the sensitivity of peel strength to the degree of cure. The shear strength and Bell peel strength of the adhesive cured at various curing time were shown in Table 2. It was obvious that with the curing time of the adhesive prolonged, the Bell peel strength increased steadily while the shear strength changed little. After 4 hours curing, both the shear strength and Bell peel strength satisfied the requirement of 120°C curing adhesive Metlbond 1113.06. The curing time was then fixed 4 hours in the following study. Furthermore, if higher peel strength was required, the curing time can be prolonged more.

Table 2: The influence of curing time on the adhesion properties

Curing time, hours	3	4	5
Shear strength, MPa	38.8	42.7	39.0
Bell peel strength, kN/m	4.83	6.03	6.40

The Primary Mechanical Properties of SY-41

Table 3 listed the heat resistant, hygrothermal resistant and room temperature storage properties. The requirements of moderate temperature (120°C) curing adhesive film Metlbond 1113.06 were also listed in Table 3 for comparison.

Table3: The primary mechanical properties of SY-41(Typical Value)

	SY-41				Metlbond 1113.06	
	Shear strength, MPa	Retention rate,%	Bell peel strength, kN/m	Retention rate, %	Shear strength, MPa	Bell peel strength, kN/m
R.T.	42.7		6.03		>33	>6
82°C	30.8	72.1	8.87	147	>21*	>4.5*
after immersed in boiling water for 24 hours	34.1	79.8	6.75	112		
after exposure to 70°C, R.H.95-100% for 500 hours	31.0	72.6			>25	>4.5
after store at 22-26°C for 30 days	42.7	100	6.0	99.5	>33	>6

* Requirements of Metlbond1113.06 at 70°C

It can be concluded from the data in table 3 that SY-41 has a high heat resistant property, its shear strength and Bell peel strength at 82°C were higher than those of Metlbond 1113.06 at 70°C. Moreover, the Bell peel strength at 82°C was 47% higher than that of at room temperature. In the mean time, SY-41 has a good hygrothermal resistant property after immersed in boiling water for 24 hours, the retention shear strength was 34.1 MPa, with a retention rate of 80%, while the Bell peel strength increases to 6.76kN/m, with a retention rate of 112%. After store at 22-26°C for 30 days, the shear strength and Bell peel strength appear no obvious decrease which means its room temperature shelf life exceeds 1 month.

CONCLUSION

SY-41 was a kind of epoxy film adhesive with high strength, high toughness, good heat and hygrothermal resistant properties. Excellent mechanical properties can be obtained when curing at 90°C, 0.1MPa for 4 hours which makes the adhesive can be used in field repair. Its room temperature shelf life exceeds 1 month.

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